

The Influence of Teacher-Related Factors in Enhancing the Tamil Language Skills of Primary Level Students

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Abstract

Teachers play a significant role in developing the Tamil language skills of primary level students. This study aims to identify the contributions of teachers in developing language skills (reading, speaking, and writing) among primary level students in Tamil medium schools within the Homagama Education Zone. To achieve this, sub-objectives were formulated to identify the strategies used by teachers to develop language proficiency, the teaching approaches employed to enhance language skills in the primary section, and the communication methods utilized by teachers. A mixed-method research approach was adopted for this study. The sample consisted of 70 teachers (selected through random sampling), 5 principals, and 5 vice-principals from schools within the Homagama Education Zone. Data were collected through questionnaires and interview schedules. Questionnaires and interviews served as the primary data collection tools. To gather information regarding teacher qualifications, experience, and the teaching strategies they utilize, both closed and open-ended questionnaires were employed. According to the findings of the study, teachers showed a very high level of engagement (Mean: 4.72) in using creative strategies such as picture stories and short essays to develop students' writing skills. Learning through play (Mean: 3.97) and the use of audio-visual aids (Mean: 4.36) also recorded significant averages. Although teachers performed well in maintaining clear communication with students (Mean: 4.14), a very high variation (SD: 6.55) was observed among teachers regarding writing skill practice. Irregular student attendance and the lack of proper parental guidance were identified as major causes of learning loss. Therefore, this study recommends the appointment of specialized resource persons at the zonal level, the improvement of technological facilities, and the necessity of

prioritizing remedial teaching by extending learning activities beyond regular school hours.

Keywords:

Language skill development, Primary section, Teacher-related factors, Homagama Education Zone. Aim of the Study

1.0. Introduction

The aim of this study is to identify the contributions of teachers in developing language skills (reading, speaking, and writing) among primary-level students in Tamil-medium schools within the Homagama Education Zone. To achieve this, the following sub-objectives have been formulated. Language development includes reading, speaking, and writing. These are classified into two types. Listening and reading are considered receptive skills, while speaking and writing are productive skills. Just as the foundation of a house is important for its strength, early childhood education is equally important for a child's development. If these skills are not developed properly, the child may face difficulties in learning and become disadvantaged in society. The development of a society's language largely depends on primary education. In that sense, the future progress of students is rooted in early childhood education. Therefore, the growth and development of education can be observed through the progress achieved at the primary level. When children receive a proper foundation in their mother tongue, they are able to learn other languages more easily. Language development begins from the child's early years. Preschool education and early childhood developmental activities play a major role in this process. These activities prepare children to read, speak, and write effectively in school. Preschools play a significant role in encouraging children's interest in these activities.

If there is a deficiency in reading, speaking, or

writing, students are considered to have weaknesses in language skills. In primary classes, teaching methods and learning guides are designed to develop these language skills systematically. However, teachers face challenges while teaching, students face challenges while learning, and difficulties also arise in applying these methods effectively. If students fail to achieve the necessary language competence at the primary level, they may struggle to progress in continuous education. As a result, they may find it difficult to face future challenges in society. Therefore, the foundation of language skills developed in the early grades becomes essential for the progress of the family, school, and society. Hence, this study focuses on identifying the contribution of teachers in developing the language skills of primary grade students in Tamil-medium schools in the Homagama educational zone. This chapter discusses the introduction to the study, background of the research, research problem, objectives of the study, research questions, hypotheses, theoretical and conceptual foundations, significance of the study, limitations of the study, and related literature review.

Objectives

1. To identify the strategies used by teachers to develop language proficiency among primary-level students.
2. To investigate the academic and professional challenges faced by teachers in developing language skills within the primary section.
3. To identify the teaching approaches utilized by teachers to enhance language skills in the primary section.
4. To identify the communication methods employed by teachers to develop language skills in the primary section.

2.0.Literature Review

Speaking, reading, and writing are the fundamental skills of a language. The role of primary education in enhancing these basic language skills is significant. Although these skills are often presented separately for clarity, it is essential to present them in an integrated manner for effective instruction (Shabani & Cotteratti, 2018). Within basic language skills, listening and reading are considered input skills, while writing and speaking are classified as output skills. Both the school environment

and the external environment play a supporting role in the development of these skills. Therefore, the role of primary education in fostering basic language development is immeasurable (Rathner, 2017). When considering "reading" within language development, it is viewed as a cognitive process. This involves implicitly and explicitly connecting thoughts, formulating questions, providing answers by linking ideas, and utilizing information to innovate in new contexts (Ruiz, 2015). Reading exerts a profound and lasting influence on a child's life, beginning in childhood and continuing throughout their lifetime. Although reading science is primarily based on research conducted in English and other languages, implementing components of the reading framework specifically within Tamil language instruction poses certain challenges.

Tamil possesses unique linguistic features that distinguish it from English and Western languages (Safeek, 2024). Speaking plays a vital role in language proficiency. While information can be conveyed through various methods—such as gestures and pictures—words remain the most effective medium for communication. Although communication involves both writing and speaking, it is estimated that three-quarters of all human communication occurs through speech (Narayanan, 2021).

Various factors influence language development in children. Intelligence is considered a primary factor; children with lower cognitive abilities or low birth weight may experience delays in the onset of speech. However, delayed language development can also occur due to various other underlying factors (Henry, 2017). Globally, achieving proficiency in the four basic language skills—speaking, reading, writing, and listening—remains a top priority. Among these, speaking is often identified as the most challenging skill for learners to master effectively (Christopher, 2017). Speaking is considered one of the most essential and desired language skills. While there are numerous strategies to enhance speaking skills in primary schools, the importance given to Tamil speaking proficiency is often neglected by both parents and students (Ramalingam, 2022).

When a child's home and social environment are saturated with slang and linguistic mixing, it directly impacts their speech patterns.

Santhanam (2008) asserts that a child's family and environment possess the power to reshape their learning methods. Deficiencies in speech often manifest as errors in writing, and incorrect pronunciation is frequently cited as a primary cause for these written mistakes. Therefore, it is highly important for teachers to model proper pronunciation and maintain linguistic purity—avoiding the mixing of other languages—while teaching.

In a rapidly changing world, it is essential to provide education that enables children to participate fully in today's and tomorrow's society. Therefore, more than traditional approaches to mother-tongue reading and writing, there is an increased need for literacy (Kinshasa, 2017). During language teaching, structured or planned play-based activities should be incorporated as an addition, and written exercises should be implemented sufficiently. By carrying this out step-by-step according to each grade level, language proficiency development can be achieved. Effective classroom management plays a vital role in overcoming learning challenges; therefore, it is necessary to examine through this study whether teachers' lesson planning is effective (Mahesan, 2009).

Regarding teaching approaches for language proficiency, visual-based learning—using images, videos, and explanatory charts—helps attract students' attention through audiovisual aids and activity-based cards (Manivannan, 2018). Additionally, nursery rhymes and word games help children understand easily. Presenting simple activities that combine songs with music and play creates enthusiasm (Jeyapal, 2017). For reading and writing practice, children should be encouraged to write words based on phonetic sounds through alphabet-based tasks (Muthukkumaran, 2018). Furthermore, student engagement can be increased through activities such as storytelling, role-playing, small dramas, and creating game models (Anitha, 2016).

The effectiveness of the teaching process significantly impacts a student's ability to understand and use the skills required for written expression. Useful teaching strategies, a supportive learning environment, skilled instructors, and thoughtfully designed teaching materials are key factors that significantly

enhance a student's proficiency in writing Tamil essays (Troia, 2017).

Integrating various modern teaching strategies

and techniques into the instruction of Tamil writing skills encourages students to engage actively and promotes high productivity in their practical applications. This approach empowers students to move beyond mere theoretical understanding and directly implement their knowledge (Nurharjanto & Widyantoro, 2020). Consequently, implementing modern teaching methods fosters a changing and productive learning environment. When students master each skill through student-centered methods, they experience greater satisfaction (Tirthayani, 2020). Research has found that teachers who incorporate friendly and fun activities can effectively engage students in language lessons. Teachers should clearly explain the objectives of a lesson in Tamil classes, ensure students master the content well, and deliver it simply and efficiently.

Speech-related activities must be diversified with highly creative tasks to engage students. Additionally, Tamil language teachers should maintain continuous communication with students

while implementing the teaching and learning process (Dayandari, 2020). Constant interaction with students helps teachers gain insights and improve their teaching effectiveness and the students' skills. In the 21st century, due to the widespread use of technology at all levels of education, students face high competition. This is why our education system needs to be enriched with the skills required for this era of globalization (Pandi et al., 2019).

Furthermore, research indicates that providing students with skills that cater to their future aspirations within the 21st-century curriculum and instruction is vital (Alismail & McGuire, 2015). Since the knowledge and understanding of teachers regarding 21st-century models are still at a developing stage, teacher proficiency remains at a moderate level (Ajis & Rahman, 2018). Teachers with limited proficiency may struggle to perform effectively and could hinder the learning process. A teacher's skill level also impacts their creative capacity within the learning environment (Hassan & Thambu, 2018). If teachers are not prepared to embrace 21st-century learning, implementing it in their instruction can become a burden (Hassan & Thambu, 2018).

Due to time constraints, dense curricula, and exam-based education systems, most teachers

continue to use traditional teaching methods in the classroom (Hakim & Ishtiaq, 2018; Mandhara & Mart, 2020; Yahya et al., 2020). Traditional teaching typically relies on lower-level cognitive processes (Krathwohl, 2002). Conversely, implementing "4C" skills (Critical thinking, Communication, Collaboration, and Creativity) involves higher-level cognitive processes. Selecting an appropriate teaching framework depends on a teacher's understanding of effective learning and 21st-century education. Ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education for all and promoting lifelong learning opportunities is a key commitment (UNESCO, 2016, p.7). In environments where literacy rates are affected by various socio-economic factors and language barriers, it is vital to bridge the gaps in educational access. This emphasizes ensuring that all learners, regardless of their background, have the opportunity to develop their literacy skills. Consequently, implementing modern teaching approaches fosters a dynamic and beneficial learning environment. The surroundings and the students' ability to effectively utilize the knowledge and skills they have acquired improve significantly. The necessity of Tamil writing skills is a crucial component in Tamil language instruction. Students are guided and

taught to write in advanced formats, including the alphabet and complete sentences.

3.0. Research Methodology

This research is conducted using a Quantitative Descriptive Survey method. This is an approach used to obtain defined data, then summarize and analyze it. Furthermore, to fully understand the various dimensions of the study, a Mixed Method is utilized. Through this, comprehensive analyses can be performed by simultaneously using both Quantitative (mathematical) and Qualitative (descriptive) information.

In the mixed-method approach, quantitative and qualitative data have been triangulated. Accordingly, following Creswell's (1999) classification, a Sequential Explanatory method was used, where the analysis of quantitative data is compared with the analysis of qualitative data to achieve and describe data triangulation.

3.1. Research Population

The primary schools of the Tamil medium schools in the Homagama Education Zone have been selected as the population for this study. A total of 70 teachers, 5 principals, and 5 vice-principals constitute the main population of the study. This is shown in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2
Research Population

School	Teachers	Principals	Vice-Principals	School
Type III		54	03	03
Type II		08	01	01
1C		08	01	01
Total		70	05	05

3.2. Research Sample

For this study, Tamil medium schools including 1C, Type 2, and Type 3 schools within the Homagama Education Zone were selected. From these schools, teachers and principals were chosen as samples using the Simple Random Sampling method. Specifically, 70 teachers were selected through structured random sampling.

Additionally, 03 principals and 03 vice-principals were selected using the Convenience Sampling method.

3.3. Data Collection

Questionnaires and interviews were used for data collection. To collect this data, the researcher first contacted the principals of

each school via telephone to obtain permission. Upon visiting the schools, information was gathered from the teachers, who completed the forms in a friendly and cooperative manner within the school premises. Interview forms were also completed with the principals. While it was challenging for teachers to complete the questionnaires during their teaching hours, they recognized the purpose of the study and completed them without hesitation, allowing the data to be collected effectively.

3.4.Data Analysis

The data collected for the purpose of the study were analyzed using SPSS software through **Descriptive Statistics**.

4.0.Data and Data Analysis

4.1.Strategies used by teachers to develop language proficiency among primary section students.

Based on the first research question, a detailed analysis was conducted regarding the types of strategies teachers employ to improve students' language proficiency. To achieve this objective, five questions were designed in the first part of the questionnaire to collect data. This data was analyzed focusing on students' basic language skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

Through this analysis, various creative strategies followed by teachers were identified. Specifically, strategies such as using various reading media to stimulate reading interest among students, and encouraging classroom

discussions and group activities to improve speaking skills, were highlighted. Furthermore, creative activities such as picture stories and short essays are provided to develop students' writing skills. Teachers also use explanatory methods to teach new words, and language-based games and puzzles to encourage classroom learning. Statistical measures such as Mean, Median, and Standard Deviation were used to identify the importance and prevalence of the aforementioned strategies.

In addition, Qualitative Insights were gathered to strengthen the quantitative data. For this purpose, information obtained through interviews conducted with principals was subjected to the study. The profound views shared by principals regarding the contribution of teachers and the unique techniques they employ in students' language development were compared with the results obtained through the questionnaire. Detailed explanations for research question one have been summarized in this analysis.

4.2.Use of various reading media to stimulate reading interest.

Information was obtained regarding the various reading media used by teachers to stimulate students' reading interest. This can be seen in **Table 6.1.2**.

Table 6.2.1

Use of various reading media to stimulate reading interest

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	3	4.5
Agree	8	12.1
Neutral	6	9.1
Disagree	30	45.5
Strongly Disagree	13	19.7
Total	60	100

Based on **Table 6.1.2**, a detailed analysis of whether teachers use various reading media to stimulate students' reading interest is provided below.

Analysis of the Use of Reading Media: A total of 60 teachers participated in this study. Upon deep examination of the statistical summary based on their opinions, the following key points were identified: **Dominance of Negative Responses:** A majority of the participating teachers (45.5%) responded with "Disagree" regarding the use of reading media. When combined with the 19.7% of teachers who "Strongly Disagree," it becomes evident that a total of 65.2% of teachers do not appropriately utilize various reading media in their teaching and learning activities. **Low Percentage of Agreeing Teachers:** The number of teachers stating that they use modern or diverse reading media to develop students' reading skills is very low. Combining the "Strongly Agree" (4.5%) and "Agree" (12.1%) categories, only 16.6% of teachers support this view. **Neutral Stance:**

Approximately 9.1% of teachers held a neutral opinion. This may indicate that they use media only occasionally or that they lack a clear understanding of the subject.

4.3.2.Challenges Faced by Teachers in Developing Language Proficiency

This section provides a detailed explanation of the challenges faced by teachers regarding language proficiency development, modern language teaching approaches, student assessment, and meeting the individual needs of students. Additionally, it examines the challenges teachers encounter when implementing learning tools used for language development. Please refer to **Table 6.2.1** for details on the challenges faced by teachers in developing language proficiency in the primary section.

6.3.1.Table Training Received by Teachers and the Challenges They Encounter

Q.No.	Question Description	Frequency (N)	Mean	Median
6	proficiency Knowledge of modern language	50	3.18	3
7	teaching approaches	50	3.66	4
8	Ability to assess various language skills of students	50	4.06	4
9	Challenges in meeting the individual language needs of students	50	4.02	4
10	Opportunity for resources and supplementary tools for language development	50	3.02	3

In this study, \$N=50\$ participants took part. Their opinions were collected based on five key factors. Regarding the factors that received the highest scores (challenges and skills), the Assessment Skill (Question 08) obtained the highest average score (Mean 4.06) for teachers assessing students' language proficiency. This indicates that teachers have a clear understanding of assessment methods. Meeting Individual Needs (Question 09), specifically the challenges in meeting the unique language

needs of students, also received high importance (Mean 4.02). This suggests that handling diversity within the classroom remains a significant challenge.

Regarding Modern Approaches (Question 07), knowledge of modern language teaching methods stands at an average of 3.66. While this is somewhat satisfactory, it is still an area that needs further

development. The factors that received the lowest scores (facilities and opportunities) were Opportunities for Training and Guidance (Question 06), where access to sufficient training to develop language proficiency is quite low (Mean 3.18), and Resources and Tools (Question 10), where opportunities for supplementary tools and resources necessary for language development recorded the lowest average (Mean 3.02).

Teachers are proficient in assessment and in understanding the needs of students. However, the lack of necessary training opportunities and teaching resources appears to be a major deficiency. The opportunity for resources and supplementary tools (Question 10, Mean 3.02) is found to be very low. This highlights resource scarcity as a significant challenge.

6.3.2. Thematic Analysis

Based on the opinions of the principals, the challenges faced by teachers and the ways they manage them can be divided into four main themes

Student Absenteeism This is a common challenge pointed out by all types of principals. There is a continuous decline in student attendance, and some students remain completely absent from school. Encouragement and Rewards To attract students to the school environment, encouragement and providing rewards to regular students can motivate others.

Socio-Economic & Family Issues This is a major challenge, specifically in Type 3 and Type 2 schools. Factors include parents going abroad for work and an unsuitable environment at students' homes. Consequently, students are unable to carry out learning activities at home. To address the deficiencies in the home environment, more learning opportunities

2.1

should be provided to students during school hours, along with complete guidance from teachers.

Communication Barriers Complexities in language usage and information exchange are described here. This includes the use of different dialects among students and the difficulty in correctly receiving learning information. There is a need to make students realize the importance of speaking in the Tamil language and to pave the way for systematic information exchange.

Administrative approaches used by principals to manage challenges

Parent-Teacher Discussions Speaking directly with parents to resolve students' learning deficiencies. **Consultation among Teachers** Consulting with specific subject teachers to find solutions for student problems. **Resource Scarcity** Obtaining the full cooperation of available teachers to compensate for the shortage of staff.

4.4. Teaching Approaches used by Teachers to Develop Language Proficiency

This section explains the methods used during student reading—such as tone, letter sounds, and pronunciation—and the way learning resources beyond textbooks are utilized. It also describes methods to encourage students' independent thinking and creative activities, the assessment systems used to monitor language progress, and the methods of encouraging students by providing gentle guidance while correcting errors.

Please refer to **Table 6.3.1** regarding the teaching approaches used by teachers to develop language proficiency.

Table 6.4.1 Teaching Approaches for Developing Language Proficiency

Q.NO.	Question Description	Frequency (N)	Mean	Median
11.	Using a mix of Phonics (sound method) and Whole Word methods to improve students' reading skills.	50	3.36	3
12.	Utilizing external resources beyond textbooks.	50	4.18	4

13.	Encouraging students to think independently and express their creativity.	50	4.1	4
14.	Conducting continuous assessments to monitor language progress.	50	3.94	4
15.	Providing gentle guidance when correcting errors.	50	4.26	4

Statistical data regarding teaching approaches for developing Language Skills are presented. Based on this study conducted with a group of 50 participants, the impact of various teaching strategies among students and teachers has been evaluated through the Analysis of the table data. Based on the average scores (Mean), the following conclusions can be drawn:

Highest Acceptance The approach of "Providing gentle guidance while correcting errors" (Question 15) received the highest average score of 4.26. This indicates that students expect a high level of psychological support in their learning process. **Key Strategies** Using external resources beyond textbooks (Question 12 - Mean 4.18) and encouraging students' creativity (Question 13 - Mean 4.10) are considered highly important teaching approaches. **Lower Average:** The method of using a mix of Phonics and Whole Word methods (Question 11) received a lower average score of 3.36 compared to other approaches. However, it continues to remain at an intermediate level.

All approaches from Question 12 to 15 maintain a Median of 4.00. This shows that most respondents accepted these methods as "highly essential." Overall, it is evident that students prefer a gentle approach when errors are pointed out and a broad learning environment that goes beyond textbooks. The practice of providing gentle guidance while correcting errors (Question 15, Mean 4.26) is followed by teachers as the most effective approach.

6.4.2 Thematic Analysis

Based on the responses from principals, a Thematic Analysis was conducted regarding the teaching resources for developing students'

language skills. The use of Modern Technology & Multimedia was a strongly emphasized area by principals across various schools. Significant importance has been given to Listening and Viewing skills in language learning.

Resources used include Audio, Video lessons, computer, laptop, and Multimedia Projector. Delivering lessons to students easily and interestingly through modern devices. Alongside technology, traditional methods to develop reading and writing skills are also highlighted. Resources used include storybooks, magazines, short stories, and library usage. Activities such as writing stories and poems; principals have recommended an approach that transforms the traditional language from just a subject into an experience.

Role Play, Activity Center method, field trips, and arts activities. Encouraging students to use the language without hesitation through practical application. The view of a Category 3 principal reveals that resources go beyond physical objects to include the human resources needed to use them correctly. Modern training for teachers, new teacher handbooks, assessment methods, and project plans. Ensuring that teaching materials and character-building inputs reach teachers and students in a timely manner.

2.2

4.5. Techniques and support required for teachers to handle challenges in developing the language skills of primary section students

What techniques and supports are available for teachers to overcome challenges in developing the language skills of primary students? With that objective, creating language understanding through clear and simple repetitive songs. Are teachers encouraging students to speak and ask questions in the classroom without fear? Additionally, sharing information regarding

students' language development with parents. Furthermore, teachers observing students' body language and emotional expression, as well as explanations regarding visual and audio resources, are covered. See **Table 6.5.1** regarding what techniques and support teachers need to handle the challenges

in developing the language skills of primary section students.

6.5.1 Table
Techniques and support required for teachers to handle challenges in developing the language skills of primary section students

Q. N o	Question Details	Frequency (N)	Mean	Median
	Creating language understanding			
	through clear and simple repetitive			
16	songs	50	4.14	4
	Encouraging students to speak and			
	ask questions in the classroom			
17	without fear	50	4.36	4
	Sharing information regarding			
	students' language development with			
18	parents	50	4.22	4
	Observing students' body language			
19	and emotional expression	50	4.22	4
20	Utilizing visual and audio resources	50	4.24	4

This indicates that teachers are closely observing the overall development of students. "Clear Communication" (Question 16), achieving language understanding through clear and simple communication, received a mean value of 4.14. The overall result shows that the Median for all questions is 4.00. This confirms that most teachers follow these communication methods at a level of "Strongly Agree" or "Agree."

Analysis of communication methods used by teachers with students and parents: In the data analysis study of teachers' communication methods, responses were received and analyzed from 50 participants (N=50). For this, the Mean and Median values were calculated. The method with the highest value (Question 17),

"Using additional resources such as stories, songs, and videos," holds the highest mean (4.36). This indicates that teachers strongly recognize the importance of modern media in teaching and learning.

Utilizing visual and audio (Audio-Visual) resources (Question 20) received a mean value of 4.24. This plays a significant role in attracting students' attention. Sharing language development progress and observing body language (Questions 18 and 19)—both sharing language development with parents and observing students' body language—carry an equal mean value of 4.22.

This indicates that teachers are closely observing the overall development of students. "Clear Communication" (Question 16),

achieving language understanding through clear and simple communication, received a mean value of 4.14. The overall result shows that the Median for all questions is 4.00. This confirms that most teachers follow these communication methods at a level of "Strongly Agree" or "Agree."

4.6. Thematic Analysis

A Thematic Analysis was conducted based on the responses received from various school principals regarding improving the Tamil language skills of primary school students in the Homagama Educational Zone. In analyzing the principals' responses, the following themes emerged: Human Resources & Guidance The most important point highlighted by all types of principals is the shortage of qualified guides. The need for a dedicated, excellent Tamil teacher counselor and a responsible officer specifically for the Tamil language department has been emphasized. It was pointed out as a major deficiency that there are not enough resource persons at the zonal level to conduct workshops and provide subject-related clarifications.

Teacher Motivation & Development The attitude and skills of teachers have a direct impact on the language skills of students. There are challenges in raising the quality of teaching due to the lack of formal workshops and guidance for teachers. Motivation Mechanisms to motivate teachers at the zonal level are essential. Teachers should adopt psychological approaches such as speaking kindly to students, listening to their ideas, and building their self-confidence (Opinion of a Category 2 Principal). Learning Resources & Infrastructure Principals believe that textbooks alone are not enough to develop language skills. Supplementary books, magazines, children's newspapers, and additional reading materials should be made available at the classroom level.

The need for modern technology, specifically Electronic devices and computing equipment for teaching and learning activities, has been emphasized by the IC school principal. Regarding Co-curricular Activities & Monitoring, proper platforms are required to showcase and measure students' talents. Competitive Opportunities Creating zonal-level

competitions and platforms for students to express their talents through the Tamil language. Proper Monitoring: Systematic monitoring and Assessment tools are essential to measure student progress. Based on these

research findings, it is clear that focus must be placed on both "Human Resource Allocation" and "Learning Resource Provision" to improve Tamil language skills in the Homagama zone.

3.0 5.0. Research Findings

Following the data collection and analysis conducted in Tamil medium schools within the Homagama Educational Zone, the decisions reached through the summary of principals' interviews are as follows: According to the research, under the category of teacher-related factors influencing the development of primary students' Tamil language skills, teachers have realized they must use modern methods suited for students while applying their teaching strategies. The findings of this research state that by using strategies that attract students, the challenges faced during teaching can be overcome.

Regarding students' use of reading media, the research found a low level of positive consensus among teachers concerning modern reading media. It has been identified that teachers' lack of awareness and non-use of modern reading media has resulted in a minimal use of various media to develop the reading, speaking, and writing skills of primary students; the necessity for this is highlighted at the end of this research. There is a strong correlation between the diversity of teaching strategies used by teachers and the skill development of students. Therefore, the conclusion of this study is that teachers must identify and implement these strategies effectively. The research findings show that a gap exists between teaching strategies and the students' learning experience. Based on this research data, it was concluded that it is essential to restructure activities more creatively to stimulate students' thinking.

Principals mention the shortage of resource persons as a significant challenge. Perhaps if the resources and the necessary support for them had not affected teaching, this shortage would not have been considered a challenge. It

can be concluded from this research that teaching effectiveness is greatly influenced by school resources and guidance. To improve the quality of teaching, systematic motivation and monitoring mechanisms at the zonal level are essential. According to this research data, it can be concluded that to enhance Tamil language skills in the Homagama zone, both modern technological resources and human resource guidance must be integrated.

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